

Assessment and Demonstration

Testing & certification experience to qualify a family of colored BIPV modules

Building integration of photovoltaics always has to deal with two different standardization and regulation schemes: one derived from the building requirements, the other one from the electro-technical field. Compared to traditional modules, BIPV elements have variable characteristics such as colour, size and materials. For this reason their qualification could be very expensive and difficult, committing the producer to invest time and money. Within the project we have developed a procedure to simplify this aspect and limit the number of modules to be tested, by guaranteeing the quality of a larger family of modules.

BIPV quality, standards, normative compliance, testing procedures, coloured modules

target audience (Regulation makers / Owners & other decision makers / Architects & engineers / Suppliers & companies)

Building integration of photovoltaics always has to deal with two different standardization and regulation schemes: one derived from the requirements from the building sector, often regulated in local building codes, and international ISO standards, the other one from the electrical side, complying with international IEC standards. Further mandatory, but not fully harmonized local regulations are in force in building sector. While one standard, the EN 50583 series "Photovoltaic in Buildings" [1], was issued in 2016 at the European level, different new work item proposals were launched internationally, and several within the IEC technical committee TC82 (Photovoltaics). What steps does a BIPV module manufacturer need to get a qualification of his product? How much can it cost?

A specific example of a full qualification program and type approval for a family of colored BIPV modules, designed by HSLU and Üserhuus, has been set-up by SUPSI PVLab, based on the technical specification IEC TS 62915 – "Photovoltaic (PV) modules – Type approval, design and safety qualification – Retesting". To this end, one type of multi-colored BIPV module has been manufactured and submitted to a full testing program, in order to achieve an IEC parent product type approval certificate, according to a combined design qualification (IEC 61215) and safety (IEC 61730) test sequence [2,3].

The principle of conformity assessment has been adopted to determine whether the family of multi colored BIPV modules adheres to all the specified safety, reliability and durability requirements, as laid down in the applicable IEC International Standards for standard PV modules (IEC 61215:2016 series and IEC 61730:2016 series), and analyzing beforehand some possible modifications and additional requirements introduced by the final intended BIPV applications.

In particular, the third party conformity assessment method (where independent parties carry out product evaluation and testing) has been used, primarily to save cost and time by:

- Reducing the number of steps needed for international certification
- Eliminating duplicate testing
- Testing only one sample among structurally similar products
- Requiring only certain limited tests for the upgraded or modified product
- Achieving direct acceptance by regulators, retailers and vendors in many countries

//// active interfaces

Figure 1: Tested module with relative efficiency 75%, 72 mono-cells, active wire 1972 x 1000 mm frameless glass-glass 2x4mm. This module, due to the new layering, namely the colouring of the front glass, has been subjected to a full qualification program and type approval.

Fourteen identical samples of the parent product (as in the picture above) have been submitted to the full combined test sequence (which investigates more than 100 parameters of the module for a duration of about 4 months). The performed tests can be grouped in:

- Electrical performance tests
- Electrical safety tests
- Mechanical stress tests
- Durability tests.

After the full testing program above has been successfully passed, the internationally recognized IECCE – CBTL certificate can be issued. The definition and production of the right parent module is crucial in order to speed up the qualification process and to cover a large number of possible module variations. For this reason we have designed the parent module with the following characteristics: 6 different colors, 3.2mm x 2 glass thickness, 1972x1000mm dimension. With this approach, according to the retesting guideline, the qualification can be extended automatically to all the BIPV module variants with higher or lower output power (by 10 % or more, due to the variation of the transmittance of the coloring layer caused by the different glass colors), while retaining the identical design, size cell process. This qualification can then be further extended to a whole family of multi-colored BIPV modules of identical design and cell process, but with different colors and 20% larger dimensions.

If one of these limits is exceeded (i.e. by increasing the length or module area by more than 20%) the module manufacturer has to repeat some of the tests for the new BIPV module type (such as the thermal cycling test, the damp heat test or the module breakage test).

Once this test have been completed and fully passed, the module can be used for the purpose it has been designed for. The responsibility to properly design and build the BIPV system (either as part of the roof or the façade) lies with the professional in charge of the work (such as the façade manufacturer/planner, or the structural engineer). In this case, in addition to the above-mentioned regulations specific to the module and its electrical qualification, all the requirements imposed by the CPR 305/2011 and the local construction regulations must be respected.

As demonstrated for the case studies conducted in the Active Interfaces project, such a methodology shall be applied for each BIPV project, because the required performances can vary depending on the project location, the building's geometry and typology, the use case, as well as the envelope system and the specific conventional PV module.

References

- [1] EN 50583:2016 Photovoltaics in Buildings (part 1: BIPV modules and part 2: BIPV system).
- [2] IEC 61215:2016 Terrestrial photovoltaic (PV) modules - Design qualification and type approval.
- [3] IEC 61730:2016, Photovoltaic (PV) module safety qualification
- [4] Regulation (EU) No 305/2011. European Construction Product Regulation